

Bioethanol Production from Godere (Taro Root) (*Colocasia Esculenta*) and Sweet Potato (*Ipomoea Batatas*) using *Saccharomyces Cerevisiae*

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ABSTRACT

This research aims at utilizing taro root and sweet potato for the production of bio-ethanol by using the yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. The milled samples of 50gm from each sample were taken then passed through pretreatment, hydrolysis, fermentation and distillation process respectively to produce bio-ethanol. The effects of biomass concentration, acid concentration, temperature and time on distilled and dilute acid hydrolysis were investigated. The milled taro root and s.potato were hydrolysed by distilled water and by dilute sulfuric acid (1, 2, 3 and 4) with (6.25, 7.14, 8.33, 10.00, 12.5 and 16.61 % w/v) of biomass concentration at temperature of (room, 30, 35, 40 and 45°C) for 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 days. The result showed that the maximum sugar content (83.14 and 86.66 % w/w by phenol-sulfuric acid and Fehling method respectively for taro root, 88.51 and 88.33 % w/w by phenol-sulfuric acid and Fehling method respectively for s.potato,) was obtained from hydrolysis of 10 % biomass concentration containing 2% sulfuric acid at 35 °C for 4 days. The optimized hydrolyzate sample was fermented at optimized pH, 6.00, yeast extract, 4 g/100 mL and at 32.5 °C for 4 days. The maximum 8.075 and 8.77 % w/v for godere and s.potato respectively ethanol content was achieved at 4 days fermentation time. However, as fermentation time increased from 4 days it resulted in decreasing ethanol content.

Keyword: Bioethanol, *Taro root*, *s. potato*, *hydrolysis*, *fermentation*, *S. cerevisiae* and *SHF*.

INTRODUCTION

Due to the potential exhausting nature of fossil fuels and the increasing price of petroleum together with environmental concerns, the search for alternative renewable fuels has attracted great attention in worldwide (Sharma et al., 2008). Attention has been given to the conversion of biomass into fuel ethanol, which are the cleanest liquid fuel alternative to non-renewable fossil fuels. The rise in prices and environmental problems caused by fossil fuels has contributed to this recent interest from economic and ecological perspectives. (Lin et al., 2006).

1.1. The Statement of the Problem

Ethanol is an excellent candidate to replace gasoline, and it has traditionally been produced mainly from sugars or starch (Matsakas L., et al).

The world is faced with two major problems, first being the sharp depletion of fossil-fuel reserves and second is the uncontrolled environmental degradation. Combustion of ethanol results in relatively low emission of volatile organic compounds, carbon monoxide and nitrogen oxides. The emission and toxicity of ethanol are lower than those of fossil fuels such as petroleum, diesel etc. Hence there is a need to explore the possibility of using alternative energy sources, which are as efficient as oil and can be used as an alternative or by blending with present fuels. (Tahir, A. et al., 2010).

1.2. Objective of the study

1.2.1. General objective

The objective of this study was to produce bioethanol from godere (taro root) and sweet potato by using co-culture of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*.

1.2.2. Specific objectives

- ❖ To produce bioethanol from godere (taro root) and sweet potato by hydrolysis in distilled water and in different

concentration of dilute sulfuric acid and fermentation.

- ❖ To determine the optimum conditions for hydrolysis and fermentation of godere (taro root) and sweet potato for bioethanol Production.
- ❖ To determine whether or not the godere (taro root) and sweet potato will be a feasible source of bioethanol.
- ❖ To compare amount of bioethanol produced from godere (taro root) and sweet potato in which both are root crops.

1.3. Significance of the study

Supply of fossil fuels causes harm to human health and contributes to the greenhouse gas (GHG) emission. The reduction of GHG pollution is the main advantage of utilizing biomass conversion into ethanol. Ethanol contains 35% oxygen that helps complete combustion of fuel and thus reduces particulate emission that pose health hazard to living things. (Ali et al., 2011 and Wyman, 1996).

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. Procedure of Experiment

The study was aimed at optimization of acid hydrolysis in the production of ethanol from Godere and s. potato. Godere and s. potato were collected from Teppi area and Temenja yazi. Those were collected in plastic bags and transported to the MTU laboratory for ethanol analysis. The following methods were followed. This section describes about the methodologies and approaches of how experiments were done in this research; it included all steps and procedures of the experiments.

2.2. Collection and Processing of Sample

Godere (taro root) and sweet potato were collected in polyethylene bags from Sheka zone of Tepi and Bench Maji zone of Temenja yazi town and will transport to the MTU chemistry laboratory. Sample preparation process include: manual size reduction (knife cutting), drying and grinding after the samples were collected.

Godere (taro root) and sweet potato of each of 13kg will be used for the sample preparation. It is cut by knife into pieces of about 3-5cm length for drying and grinding. Sample drying will be carried out using sun to obtain easily crushable material.

After drying, the sample were grinded with electrical grinder. The maximum particle sizes of the ground mixed sample are 1-2 mm. The sample of larger particle size than 2 mm will ground over and over again until all particle size became 1-2 mm. The sample will be kept at room temperature until the next stage of experiment. Grinding of taro and sweet potato into powder form increases the surface area of the sample which enhances the contact between hemicellulose and cellulose with dilute acid to reduce cellulose crystallinity. (Teshager Mekonnen et al., 2015, Onuki, 2005).

2.2.1. Pretreatment

The size of the taro root and sweet potato were mechanically reduced using a grinder. 0.5% sulfuric acid will be added for 50g of each samples solution since a higher yield is obtained with a catalyst like H₂SO₄. The mixture was heated under at a temperature of 125 - 130 °C and 25 psi pressure for 1 hour. It was again dry with hot air at 35°C. Samples were collected from the pretreated material for analysis. The purpose of the pretreatment is to remove lignin, reduce cellulose crystallinity and increase the porosity of the materials. Confirmatory tests by iodine (test for the presence of starch) will be carried out to ascertain that the pretreated material is actually free of lignin it produced helically coiled blue complex. (Mishra, 2011).

2.2.2. Hydrolysis

Dilute or concentrated acids breakdown the cellulose and hemicellulose polymer in lignocellulosic biomass to form individual sugar molecules which can be fermented in to alcohol. (Teshager Mekonnen et al., 2015, Wyman, 1996).

50g of each godere (taro root) and sweet potato grinded were used for each triplicate experiment and the factors for hydrolysis is time (1-5 days), hydrolysis temperature (Room temperature, 30, 35, 40 and 45°C), acid concentration (0 to 4%) and biomass concentration %w/v (6.25, 7.14, 8.33, 10.00, 12.50 and 16.61). The raw material (substrate) will be hydrolyzed by dilute acid hydrolysis method by adding to the pretreated material.

2.2.3. Determination of sugar content

The amount of sugar content in the godere (taro root) and sweet potato hydrolyzate can be determined using two methods

1. Fehling method
2. Phenol-Sulfuric acid method

2.2.3.1. Fehling method

$$\text{Sugar content(\%)} = \frac{300mL.f}{V} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where: f is Fehling factor (0.051), V is volume used in the titration (titrate value) (ml) and mL is milliliter.

2.2.3.2. Phenol-sulfuric acid method

In hot acidic medium glucose is dehydrated to hydroxymethyl furfural. This forms yellow-brown colored product with phenol and has absorption maximum at 490 nm. Phenol-Sulphuric Acid Method is the easiest and reliable method amongst the quantitative assays for carbohydrate estimation. (Krishnaveni et al, 1984). The method is simple, quick, sensible, and the results are reproducible. The total sugar concentration is determined by spectrophotometry at 490 nm wavelength of glucose absorbance and the quantification is made from calibration curve using glucose as standard and calculation is performed by equation of the linear regression obtain from calibration curve. (Dubois, 1956 and Krishnaveni et al., 1984).

2.2.4. Standard and Reagent Solution Preparation

To determine the Calibration curve for standard glucose, 1mL of each of the standard solutions was pipetted out and takes into a separate test tube. Then 1mL phenol reagent and 5mL of sulfuric acid was added. The mixture was kept at room temperature for 10 min. After 10 min shake the contents in the tubes and place in a water bath at 25–30°C for 20 min. Then the absorbance was read at 490 nm by using UV-visible spectrophotometer (NV203 Spectrophotometer). Then the amount of total sugare content present in the sample solution will be calculated using the standard graph.

$$Y=AX+B \quad (2)$$

Where, Y, is absorbance of the sample, X is the concentration of the standard in g/mL, A is the y-intercept and B, is the slope, and then the concentrations of the samples in (g/mL) will be obtained by using Equ. 9 from the calibration curve:

$$x = \frac{Y-B}{A} \quad (3)$$

The total sugar contents were calculated and expressed as gram glucose equivalents (GE) per 50g of samples and are calculated from Equ.10: (Miliauskas, 2004).

$$C = \frac{XVDf}{m} \quad (4)$$

Where; C is amount of sugar content, g/g sample extract, in GE; V is the volume extract, Df is dilution factor, m is weight of the sample, X is the concentration of glucose established from the calibration Curve (g/mL).

2.2.5. Fermentation

Before adding the yeast, the pH of the solution was adjusted. The fermentation studies was carried out using baker's yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) in the hydrolysates obtained from pretreated and acid hydrolyzed godere (taro root) and banana peel. The hydrolysates were filtered and specific gravity measured by hydrometer before fermentation. The pH of the fermentation medium was adjusted to 4, 4.5, 5, 5.5, 6 and 6.5 by adding required amount of 4 M NaOH and 2.5M HCl to accommodate yeast growth. The yeast was added at a rate of 2, 3, 4 and 5g/100mL.

2.2.6. Distillation

Distillations were the last step in the production of ethanol from godere (taro root) and banana peel experiments. It is the method used to separate two liquid based on their different boiling points. However, to achieve high purification, several distillations are required. It is the purifications steps. In this experiment separation is used by distillation set up at a temperature of 85°C for 3hrs. (Talebniya et al., 2005 and Faga, 2010).

2.3. Yield calculations

The yields of alcohol were determined by distillation and measuring densities of distillates. The concentration of ethanol (%w/v) will be calculated from hydrometer and Pycnometer readings.

2.3.1. Hydrometer reading;

The Hydrometer measures the density (Specific Gravity) of the liquid it is floating in. Sugar and water are denser than alcohol. As the yeast consumes the sugar and turns it into alcohol the Hydrometer sinks lower in the liquid. It can be express using the following equation 10. (Igwe et al., 2012 and Park, 2000).

$$\text{Ethanol \% (w/v)} = 126.58 \left(\frac{OSG - FSG}{OSG} \right) \quad (5)$$

Where; 126.58 is from; (Specific gravity of water / Specific gravity of pure ethanol), OSG is original specific gravity (specific gravity before fermentation) and FSG is Final specific gravity

(specific gravity after fermentation).

2.3.2. Pycnometer reading;

Specific gravity of ethanol can be determined using Equ.11. (Igwe et al., 2012 and Fadel, M. 2000).

$$\text{Specific gravity of sample} = (X_2 - X_1) / (X_3 - X_1) \quad (6)$$

Where: X_1 is weight (g) of empty Pycnometer, X_2 is weight (g) of Pycnometer + sample and X_3 is weight (g) of Pycnometer + water

2.4. Metal Analysis

In this study metals such as Fe, Mg, Ca, Pb, and Cr were selected to determine their concentration in ethanol yield of godere (taro root) and sweet potato. A series of standard concentration is prepared. Determinations of each metal concentration were performed by using *inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectrometry* (ICP- Spectroscopy, ULTIMA-2). (Hossain et al., 2011 and Rocha et al, 2010).

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. Optimization of Different Parameters for Hydrolysis

The effect of different parameters on the amount of sugar formed was studied. The sugar content of the godere and s.potato was determined by Fehling and phenol-sulphuric method.

From Fehling method; equal amount of Fehling A and B are mixed together in a flask. The hydrolyzed and filtered samples are neutralized with 2.5M HCl and 4M NaOH and transferred in to the burette. The solution in the flask were titrated with burette solution in boiling conditions until disappearance of blue color and the volume at which brick red color observed were recorded. For each sample the sugar content is calculated here under.

A. Before titration B. At end point (brick red color). C. Red precipitates due to Cu^{+1} .

Figure 1. Experimental observation of Fehling method for total sugar determination.

From phenol sulfuric acid method, the amount of sugar content, which was expressed as glucose equivalent (GE) was calculated from the calibration curve of glucose standards. The standard solutions were prepared in five different concentrations, which were 0.04, 0.08, 0.12, 0.16 and 0.2g/mL. From the calibration curve ($y = 0.087X + 0.001$; $R^2 = 0.994$), the concentrations of unknown sugar samples can be determined as follows.

Table 1: Absorbance of glucose standard with different concentrations

Glucose concentration(g/ml)	Absorbance
0.04	0.005
0.08	0.008
0.12	0.011
0.16	0.015
0.2	0.019

Figure 2: Calibration curve of glucose standard for determination of total sugar content

3.1.1. Optimization of biomass concentration

The effect of substrate (biomass) concentration 50g sample in 800, 700, 600, 500, 400 and 300ml of distilled water containing 2% of sulfuric acid or (6.25, 7.14, 8.33, 10, 12.5, and 16.61) %w/v was investigated to study their effect on sugar yield.

The hydrolysis process was performed at 30°C, for 48hrs. The highest sugar content (60.41 and 63.02%w/w of taro root and s.potato respectively) were obtained at 10% biomass concentration. With increasing substrate concentration, the amount of sugar content increased.

3.1.2. Optimization of the Acid Concentration

It shows that 2% dilute sulfuric acid hydrolysis is more effective in simple sugar production than distilled water and dilute sulfuric acid of different concentrations (1, 3, and 4%) hydrolysis. The result showed that the amount of sugar obtained increases as the acid concentration increases from 0-2% and decreases as the acid concentration increases from 2-4% and reaches maximum in 2% acid hydrolysis.

The decrease of sugar content in acid treated samples with increasing of acid concentration from 2-4% may be due to degradation of monomeric sugars (xylose, glucose) to furfural and HMF or may be derived from dehydrating or oxidizing by sulfuric acid on glucose or it could be attributed from the conversion of glucose to levulinic and formic acid which leads to decrease in glucose yield. These substances are toxic substances for yeast and can inhibit the yeast growth (Nutawan *et al.*, 2010).

3.1.3. Optimization of Hydrolysis Temperature

To know the optimum temperature for sugar production, the hydrolysis media were kept at room temperature, 30, 35, 40 and 45°C.

The sugar yield increase due to the increase temperature from 25°C (room) to 35°C and maximum at 35°C. Beyond this level the sugar content decreases significantly. The maximum sugar yield at 35°C was 75.28 and 82% of taro root and s.potato respectively. At low temperatures, a metabolic function was reduced and it slows the rate of conversion of substrate into reduced sugar. A reason behind significant lower production of sugar at high temperature is degradation of sugar in to unwanted materials. Overall, these results indicate that extreme temperature had an unfavorable effect on sugar conversion samples (Sahu, 2014 and Nutawan *et al.*, 2010).

3.1.4. Optimization of hydrolysis time

Sugare concentration increases from 1 to 4 days. As hydrolysis time increased from 4 days it resulted in decreasing sugar content. The reason for this could be that longer residence time makes the sugars degraded to form inhibitors (furfural and HMF) (Nutawan

et al., 2010 and Idi et al., 2011).

Therefore, 2% sulfuric acid, 10% biomass concentration, 35°C temperature and 4 days residence time were selected as the optimum conditions for hydrolysis of taro root and s.potato for bioethanol production.

Table 2: Literature data; Comparison of amount of sugar yield from different materials

Types of feedstocks	Amount of sugar content % (w/w)	References
Coffee husk	90	Omprakash Sahu, 2014
Rise husk	70	Verma, 2011
Olive-tree biomass	83	Kumar et al., 2009
Sweet potato	78.19	Kumar et al, 2014
Switchgrass	90	Kumar et al., 2009
Finger millet straw	79.04	Teshager. et al...2014
Taro root	86.66	This work
S.potato	88.51	This work

3.2. Optimization of Different Parameters for Fermentation

3.2.1. Effect of pH

The ethanol yield increased significantly from pH 4.0 to 6.0 beyond this level there is decrease in ethanol yield. Fadel (2000) reported that high ethanol production was obtained by using initial pH 5.0 to 6.0. It was also shown that no ethanol production exists lower than pH 4.0.

3.2.2. Effect of yeast extract on ethanol production

It shows that as the concentration of yeast extract increased from 2 to 4 g/100ml, ethanol production was also increased from 5.14 and 5.44 to 6.58 and 6.74% of taro root and s.potato by *S. cerevisiae* respectively; but above this concentration, ethanol production was decreased when taro root and s.potato were used as substrates.

3.2.3. Effect of temperature

The ethanol yield increase due to the increase temperature from 25 to 32.5°C with the incubation of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. Beyond this level the ethanol content decreases significantly. The maximum ethanol yield at 32.5°C was 7.83 % for both taro root and s.potato from 4 days of fermentation time.

At low temperatures, a metabolic function was reduced and it slows the rate of conversion of substrate into ethanol (Hossain and Fazlily, 2010). Further, the increasing temperature reduced the percentage of ethanol production and it is mainly due to denaturation of the yeast cells (Periyasamy et al., 2009).

3.2.4. Effect of Fermentation Time

For the study of fermentation time dependency of ethanol concentration, the hydrolysates obtained from hydrolysis of the substrates were collected and used for the subsequent fermentation experiments. This experiment was done based on the above optimum conditions. The fermentation was carried out at different time periods, i.e., 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 days under optimum conditions.

Maximum ethanol productions were observed after 4 days fermentation (8.08 and 8.77% for taro root and s.potato respectively). Further increase in time period resulted in decrease

in ethanol production.

Table 3: Literature data; Comparison of ethanol production from different residues

Types of feedstocks	Ethanol production % (w/v)	References
Groundnut hulls	6.2	Ali et al., (2011)
Rotten apple waste	8.3-9.8	Tahir and Sarwar, 2012
Jerusalem artichoke	8.8	Thuesombat et al., (2007)
Corn semolina	8	Nikoli et al., (2008)
Cassava effluent	5.74-14.55	Akponah. E and Akpomie, O, 2012
Mango juice	8.5%	Reddy and Reddy, (2007)
Rice husks	5.5	Ali et al., (2011)
Cassava starch	5.9	Gunasekaran and Chandra, (2007)
Corn husk	2.72	Oyeleke and Jibrin, (2009)
Prosopis Juliflora	5	Negusu Tefera, (2009)
Finger millet straw	7.2	Teshager. M. et al...2014
Taro root	8.08	Present work
S.potato	8.77	Present work

The output of this experiment may contribute to the effect of controlling the invasiveness of the samples (If it is utilized in such a system, provided that the cost-benefit analysis favors its exploitation). The result also revealed that ethanol obtained from taro root and s.potato is a promising substituent for other agricultural products such as mango juice, cassava and corn.

3.3. Metal analysis

As indicated in Table 22, the concentration of the metals in was obtained for taro root as 0.21, 0.27, 0.97, 0.53 and 0.37 and s.potato 0.37, 0.11, 0.91, 0.61 and 0.59 for Cr, Pb, Mg, Fe, and Ca in mg/L respectively.

Table 4: Concentration of Metals in Ethanol from the Sample.

Types of metal	Concentration (mg/L)	
	Taro root	S.potato
Cr	0.21	0.37
Pb	0.27	0.11
Mg	0.97	0.91
Fe	0.53	0.61
Ca	0.37	0.59

This is a good sign of bioethanol as lead can affect the engine emission. Generally most of the elements followed the ASTM standard that is better for engine use. (Iqbal et al., 2010, Rocha et al., 2010 and Hossain et al., 2011).

3.4. Characterization

3.4.1. Infrared spectroscopy (IR)

One of the most common applications of infrared spectroscopy is to the identification of organic compounds by their functional group such as O-H (broad band) for alcohol stretch from 3600-3400cm⁻¹

Figure 3: Infrared spectroscopy (IR) for taro root

Figure 4: Infrared spectroscopy (IR) for s.potato

3.4.2. Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy(NMR)

NMR is excitation of the nucleus of atoms through radiofrequency radiation. It provides information about molecular structure and atom connectivity i.e hydrogen and carbon environment.

The position of each group in the structure ($\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$) from the number of peaks in each signal.

- ❖ CH_3 was triplet indicate that the CH_3 is adjacent to two protons that is CH_2
- ❖ CH_2 was quartet, indicates that this group is adjacent to three protons that is CH_3 group.
- ❖ OH singlet and absorbs downfield indicates that the proton is attached with electronegative atom that is oxygen.

Remember for C-NMR that each peak identifies a carbon atom in a different environment within the molecule. In this case there are two peaks because there are two different environments for the carbons. The carbon in the CH_3 group is attached to 3 hydrogens and a carbon. The carbon in the CH_2 group is attached to 2 hydrogens, a carbon and oxygen.

Figure 5: H-NMR for Godere (taro root)

Figure 6: C-NMR for Godere (taro root)

Figure 7: H-NMR for S.potato

Figure 8: C-NMR for S.potato

4. CONCLUSION

The bioethanol productions from taro root and s.potato and optimization test have been done. The optimization study showed that the highest bioethanol concentration of 8.08 and 8.77% for taro root and s.potato respectively were observed under the optimum conditions of with dilute sulfuric acid hydrolysis and fermentation time of 4 days held at 32.5 °C with baker yeasts, which is appreciable.

The concentration of ethanol obtained by the dilute acid hydrolysis of taro root and s.potato, which are 8.08 and 8.77% for taro root and s.potato respectively were highly satisfactory compared to the maximum amount of ethanol obtained from the acid hydrolysis of groundnut hulls (6.2%), enzymatic fermentation of mango juice (7-8.5%) depending on the type of mango specie, 8% of ethanol formed from corn semolina hydrolyzate and 5.74-14.55% from cassava effluent depend on fertilizer and types of salt used.

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